

Presentation with Myocardial infarction in COVID-19 patients: A Narrative review

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Abstract

This focused review is designed to analyze the myocardial injury associated with COVID-19. We aim to gather relevant information conducted in different parts of the world that describes the forementioned relationship.

Methodology: For this study, a total 10 of studies were included. We searched electronic articles, from November 2019 to January 2021, on PubMed, Cochrane, Web of Science, online Willey library, and Science Direct websites by using keywords related to myocardial infraction and Corona virus.

Results: We observed the severity of myocardial injury in COVID patients and found elevated levels of troponin as a result of myocardial inflammation. Also, we selected studies that compared the myocardial injury events before COVID and during the COVID period. During analysis, we observed that 7-40% of researchers used the same definition of myocardial injury which they analyze with echocardiographic and electrocardiographic imaging. Myocardial injury is also responsible for high complications which may eventually result in an increased mortality rate of patients during hospital admission. Studies reflects a great association between the great amount of cardiac troponin and infectious biomarkers especially with D dimer, and other inflammatory responses including the amount of ferritin, IL-6, C-reactive protein of Covid patients. Among many patients, severe hypoxemia was observed which need mechanical ventilation.

Conclusion: We conclude that the SARS- CoV-2 infection has huge impact on cardiovascular system. We conclude that serum troponin elevations and ventricular dysfunctions are the major reasons for myocardial infarction. Other factors like comorbidities also play a vital role in MI injury. Asymptomatic MI leads to a high mortality rate which needs to be monitored at the initial stage of the disease.

Keywords

Cardiovascular system, Myocardial infraction, STEMI, Serum troponin

1. Introduction:

At the end of 2019, a new contagious disease corona virus emerged out from the city of Wuhan, China. With the 2.2 basic reproductive number, its pathological observations revealed that it is a single stranded RNA virus which has ability to rapidly start mutations [1]. The initial findings trace its history with the previous species of infections called 229E, OC43, NL63, and HKU1 which usually produce cold symptoms in human beings [2,3]. Researches indicate that this virus has many similarities with MERS COV and SARS COV which are usually caused by animals and have ability to engage human beings into fatal illness [3]. In many regions of the world, Covid

prevalence depicts that in the future this epidemic occasionally occurs in future [3,4]. Early symptoms of this deadly virus are very similar to pneumonia and it was hard for physicians to generate a distinguishing line between these two viruses at the initial stage [5]. With the help of CT, imaging physicians observed pulmonary opacity in Covid patients. In the electronic imaging of Bronchoalveolar lavage fluid of Covid patients, researchers observed crown shape virus which was emerging from viral spike proteins [6]. The rapid transmission of this disease occurs through respiratory droplets and close contact. Some studies claim that it may be transmitted by the feces of affected patients [7]. Usually, the patients had mild symptoms but in many regions, high mortality ratio of Covid was observed among the old age group [8]. In Italy and Spain majority of the affected patients were from old age groups and poor immune systems and comorbidities encourage the high probability of death among them [9]. Comorbidities especially cardiovascular disorders encourage the mortality rate of Covid patients [10]. Cardiovascular disorders are on the top list of mortality rates in the year 2017. In the year 2017, 1.7 billion deaths were reported all around the world [11]. In recent studies of Fauci et al [12], they observed a strong relationship between Covid and cardiovascular diseases. Their study depicts that increased levels of cytokines in Covid patients triggered epithelial inflammation and results in myocardial infarction [12]. Due to the high prevalence of Covid, many studies reported Covid 19 association with the cardiovascular system [13-18]. In different studies, researchers claim that every one-third of Covid patients has exposure to myocardial infarction. Generally in those studies, myocardial injury is defined as a high amount of cardiac troponin from its normal range. At the time of reporting this article Covid vaccination started in all around the world, still the number of cases and severe mutations of Covid observed day by day. The myocardial injury needs proper management through mechanical ventilation to reduce in stay hospital mortality [21,22].

This narrative review is designed to analyze the myocardial injury presented in many types of research. We aim to gather relevant information conducted in different parts of the world that describes the relationship between myocardial injury and Covid 19.

2. Methodology:

2.1. Search Strategy:

For this study, we follow the Preferred Reporting Items guideline for conducting this systematic review analysis (PRISMA) [23]. We search electronic articles from January to April on PUB Med, online Willey library, and ScienceDirect site. We use keywords like "Diagnostic ECG Imaging" OR "Myocardial infarction" OR "Diagnosis of SARS-COV19 and cardiovascular disorders" OR "Medical examination of MI" OR "primary outcomes of SARS with MI" to search relevant articles. With the help of keywords, we analyze the title, abstract aims, and objectives to extract the relevant data.

2.2. Inclusion criteria:

Articles and case studies with complete demographic information and complete medical symptoms of patients confirmed after RT-PCR were included for this research. To minimize the probability of heterogeneity we did not include echocardiography findings in our study.

2.3. Exclusion Criteria:

Articles which were written in other than English language were not included for this research. On the behalf of keywords we found seven hundred sixty-two articles. Information in the form of posters, case studies without Myocardial infraction, letters to editors, and articles with copied information was excluded from this study.

Fig 1: Inclusion Criteria according to PRISMA follow up

The evaluation of our selected data was further done into two phases first we select the data based on abstract and title. Secondly, we examine the inner text of articles and include if they were eligible to fill the inclusion criteria of our study. At the initial stage of collecting data, we found seven hundred and sixty-two articles with selected keywords. In the first screening, we excluded 162 duplicate articles and further screen out the rest of 598 articles. Later on, we omitted 502 articles with poor information on Myocardial infraction and 96 articles were further gone through the screening process. At the last stage, we found 10 articles that fulfilled the inclusion criteria and had adequate data on our topic.

We kept demographic information of patients like mean age and rang, the sample size in tabular form. We also observed the definition of myocardial injury, its impact on outcomes, STEMI events, co-morbidities, DBT of STEMI events of all selected researches.

3. Results:

In table 1 we describe all the demographic information of selected studies. The majority of the studies were selected from the European region, Chinese and only one study was of United States. The reason behind the selection was that at the initial wave of Covid,

majority of the deaths were reported from the European region especially from Italy, Spain. Results demonstrate that in these regions older age groups and male gender were more prone to Myocardial infarction. We used a quality assessment tool defined by the National Institute of Health (NIH) to evaluate the overall ratio of selected studies.

In table 2 we mention MI studies and observed the severity of Covid outcomes. From these results, we observed that a high amount of troponin causes inflammation which results in myocardial injury.

In table 3 we select studies that compared the myocardial injury events before Covid and during the Covid period along with DBT. Their results show that in many regions, STEMI cases are not reported well due to quarantine situations and fear of death. But overall Covid enhances the events of STEMI and results in in-hospital mortality.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of 10 selected studies along with Quality assessment

Author	Country	Total Sample	MI or STEMI reported patients	Mean Age	Sex		Quality assessment
					Male %	Female %	
Claeys et al [24]	Belgium	949	395/949 (41.6%)	63	75%	25%	Good
Zhou et al [15]	China	191	24/45 (17%)	56	62%	38%	Good
De Rosa et al [25]	Italy	465	197/465 (42.3%)	65.9	77%	22%	Good
Guo et al [13]	China	187	52/187 (27.8%)	58.5	48.7%	51.3%	Good
Gramegna et al [26]	Italy	47	26/47 (55.33%)	65.6	79%	21%	Good
Shi et al [14]	China	416	82/416 (19.7%)	64	49.3%	50.7%	Good
Reinstadler et al [27]	Austria	163	91/163 (55.8%)	64.3	73%	28%	Good
Shi et al [29]	China	671	Not mentioned	63	48.0%	52%	Good
Romaguera et al [28]	Spain	919	395/919 (42.9%)	62.8	80%	20%	Good
Lala et al [20]	United States	2,736	985/2736 (36.0%)	66	59.6%	40.6%	Good

Table 2: Baseline Characteristics of MI studies along with Covid outcomes.

Author	MI Definition	Impact of MI on outcomes
Shi et al	TnI serum level >99th percentile URL	51.2% cardiovascular patients had chance of in-hospital mortality
Zhou et al	High-sensitivity cardiac TnI > 28pg/ml	80.7% Patients were at high risk of in-hospital mortality (CI ranges from 10.34–620.36)
Guo et al.	TnI serum level >99th percentile URL	59.6% cardiovascular patients were at high risk of mortality overall ratio 8.9%. along with 17.3% cases detected with ventricular tachycardia and 1.5% with ventricular fibrillation
Lala et al	TnI serum level	TnI ranges from >0.03–0.09ng/ml had risk of in-hospital mortality CI (95%) ranges 1.37–2.24 and >0.09ng/ml had mortality chances 2.42–3.80 [CI 95%]
Shi et al	TnI serum level >99th percentile URL	TnI amount >0.026 had high chance of mortality with CI ranges 1.28–16.28 at 95%

Table 3: Comparison between Pre STEMI case and Post STEMI cases of Covid studies

Author	Post Covid STEMI cases	Pre Covid STEMI cases	DBT time in post Covid STEMI cases	DBT time in pre covid STEMI cases	Mean difference
Romaguera et al	395	524	24.2 ± 9.3	22.2 ± 10.7	1.9
De Rosa et al	197	268	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Not mentioned
Claeys et al	188	761	65.3 ± 60.5	56.6 ± 61.9	8.7
Reinstadler et al	91	72	60.9 ± 61	76.2 ± 127	- 15.3
Gramegna et al	26	21	72.1 ± 58.0	48.6 ± 30.2	23.4

4. Discussion:

In a year high cardiovascular morbidity was observed due to Sars Cov 2. Many researchers demonstrate that Sars Cov 2 badly affects the cardiovascular system. Many types of research demonstrate the relationship of the magnitude of host immune and amount of viral inoculum which triggers the inflammation, endothelial activation along microvascular thrombosis.

Recently many studies reported high myocardial infraction among Covid patients. Many Covid cases reported types 1 and 2 MI and poor prognosis rate because both of these types have high association with respiratory infections. Respiratory infections like pneumonia and Covid restrain the demand and supply of myocardial oxygen and its imbalance leads to myocardial infarction. The biomarkers of patients and electrocardiographic shown the probability of myocardial injury in many hospitalized Covid patients [13,14,17,19,20, 22,29]. In all selected data the definition of myocardial injury varies. This variation may be affected by patient age sex and comorbidities General definition of myocardial injury is the evidence-based serum troponin elevations which may or may not cause acute ischemic [13,14,17,19,20,29].

During analysis, we observed that 7-40% of researchers used the same definition of myocardial injury which they analyze with echocardiographic and electrocardiographic imaging. Myocardial injury is also responsible for high complications which may eventually result in an increased mortality rate of patients during hospital admission. Studies reflects a great association between the great amount of cardiac troponin and infectious biomarkers, especially with D dimer, and other inflammatory responses including the amount of ferritin, IL-6, C-reactive protein of Covid patients. Among many patients, severe hypoxemia was observed which need mechanical ventilation.

From all of the selected study, a study conducted in New York [20] includes more than 2,736 Covid patients. From these patients, they observed a 36% ratio of myocardial infarction (987 out of 2736) with a high amount of troponin (above the normal range) among the patients. The researchers concluded that the older age group of Covid patients had more exposure to high troponin which eventually causes myocardial injury as compared to those who have a normal amount of troponin. While examining the clinical history of patients they observed that 30% of patients already had cardiovascular disorders and the rest 6% were vulnerable due to many other comorbidities. Their results revealed > 0.03 ng/ml and troponin elevations which range up to 0.09 ng/ml and above that results in a high hospital mortality rate. Similar results were observed in a Chinese study in which they 671 Covid patients [29]. Other biomarkers like creatine kinase, elevations in the myocardial band, and also include elevations of N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide also plays a massive role in the high mortality ratio [30].

In all selected studies atypical symptoms of myocardial injury were observed among Covid patients. In many cases, no cardiovascular history of the patient was found and they did no complaint about any chest pain [13,14]. The onset symptoms of myocardial

infarction were observed after 14 days when infection transformed from acute to chronic stage. With these observations, it's hard to demonstrate whether myocardial injury worsens the condition of patients and increases the morbidity and mortality ratio of Covid patients. Many researchers did not perform echocardiography so we could not evaluate the severity of left ventricular function with myocardial injury. Those researchers who performed echocardiography observed that many Covid cases had right ventricular dysfunction as compared to left ventricular systolic dysfunctioning [31-33]. We did not include echocardiography findings in our analysis due to the high probability of heterogeneity and repeated information. Also, studies with echocardiography did not give any information about MI type. In our analysis, we divided STEMI patients into two groups. One was already admitted with STEMI before Covid symptoms and the other was exposed to STEMI after the chronic stage of Covid. During analysis, we observed that Covid infection increases the chance of STEMI and worsens the conditions of patients as compared to the patients who already had STEMI and were exposed to Covid later. One of the reasons we deduct that mostly post Covid cases had asymptomatic STEMI. On the other hand, during analysis, we observed that the post-Covid group has prolonged DBT time as compared to another group whereas there was no difference found in time from symptoms to FMC (in minutes) among six selected studies. We observed that type 1 MI patients had a high amount of troponin and D dimer as compared to others, but it does not increase the ratio of in-hospital mortality, whereas nonischemic myocardial infarction does.

5. Conclusion:

From the results, we conclude our narrative review on a note that the SARS- CoV-2 infection has huge impact on cardiovascular system cardiovascular system is badly influenced by SARS-CoV-2 infection. We try to define the possible pathology of these two variables with the help of selected studies. We conclude that serum troponin elevations and ventricular dysfunctions are the major reasons for myocardial infarction. Other factors like comorbidities also play a vital role in MI injury. Asymptomatic MI leads to a high mortality rate which needs to be monitored at the initial stage of the disease. We suggest that there is a huge gap to study the effect of Covid or the association of Covid with Myocardial infarction. This gap needs to be fulfilled as soon as possible with complete biomarker information.

Conflict of interest:

There was no conflict of interest between authors.

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